

THE STATE OF THE HUMAN RESOURCES POTENTIAL OF MIDDLE MEDICAL WORKERS IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Abstract: A nurse identifies the patient's main problems, makes a diagnosis, that is, collects objective and subjective data and evaluates the patient, makes a care plan, which helps to properly organize patient care and identify health problems in a timely manner. In addition to working in hospitals and clinics, teaching at universities and colleges, nurses with higher education can engage in scientific research in their specialty. Nursing is a profession, science, discipline and responsibility. Today, nursing is also considered a great resource for providing medical care and improving its quality in Uzbekistan.

Key words: Nurses, working.

The content of nursing has changed over the centuries, just as the demands of society and living conditions have changed. Today, it is very difficult to give a clear answer to the question of what nursing is. Currently, there are many definitions of this concept. Each of them was derived under the influence of a number of factors: a specific historical period, the socio-economic level and geographical location of the country, the need for nursing care, the number of nurses and the duties they perform, the views and experience of the person who explains the meaning of this term. If we ask people of different ages, any professions and social strata to define what nursing is, we will receive different interpretations. The first scientific definition of the specialty "Nursing" was given by F. Nightingale in "Notes on Nursing". She believed that nursing is "the action of using the patient's environment to promote his recovery." At the same time, the goal of nursing was formulated as follows: "To create the best conditions for the patient to activate his own powers." By "the best conditions" F. Nightingale meant cleanliness, fresh air, and proper nutrition. Calling nursing an art, she believed that this art requires "organization, practical and scientific training." F. Nightingale was firmly convinced that "nursing as a profession is essentially different from medical activity and requires special knowledge that is different from medical knowledge." One of the definitions of nursing belongs to the American nurse, teacher and researcher Virginia Henderson. In 1958, the International Council of Nurses asked her to formulate the meaning of this term and write a book on the fundamental principles of patient care. It was called "Basic Principles of Nursing Activity" and was translated into 25 languages. The definition of nursing given by V. Henderson in 1961 is still relevant today.

V. Henderson states that the unique task of the nurse is to assist a person, sick or healthy, in performing actions related to his health, recovery or peaceful death, which he would undertake himself, having the necessary strength, knowledge and will. The nurse carries out this work, helping the patient to carry out all the appointments prescribed by the doctor and to gain independence faster. She is a member of the health care team, assists others (as well as the latter to her), together with colleagues participates in the planning and implementation of the entire program of actions - be it disease prevention, recovery or support for the dying. No member of the team can impose on another such heavy duties that will interfere with the performance of immediate functions. No member of the medical staff should be distracted from the performance of his main task, despite the need to clean, keep records, register and perform other actions. All health workers must understand that the central figure is the patient, and they are all called to serve him. The efforts of the health care team will be in vain if the patient does not accept and participate in the care. The sooner the patient can take care of himself, monitor his health, and follow the doctor's orders, the better. This view of the nurse as a substitute for what the

patient lacks to be "whole," "safe," or "independent" may seem somewhat limited. But it is not. The stated goal is difficult to achieve, so the tasks and functions of a nurse are very complex.

How rare are people who are mentally and physically "whole and sound"? To what extent is good health hereditary and to what extent acquired? It is believed that the level of mental development and education is related to the state of health. And if good health is difficult to achieve for most people, then it is much more difficult for a nurse to help a person achieve this goal. She must simply "stand in the shoes" of each patient in order to understand his needs. "A nurse is sometimes conscious, sometimes unconscious, sometimes loving life, sometimes inclined to suicide. A nurse is the legs of the legless, the eyes of the blind, the support of a child, the source of knowledge and confidence for a young mother, the mouth of those too weak or withdrawn to speak." At a meeting of national representatives of the International Council of Nurses (New Zealand, 1987), the following formulation was unanimously adopted: "Nursing is an integral part of the health care system and includes activities to promote health, prevent disease, provide psychosocial assistance and care to individuals with physical and mental illnesses, as well as disabled people of all ages. Such assistance is provided by nurses both in medical and any other institutions, as well as at home, wherever there is a need for it." For a long time, nurses only carried out doctor's orders. They were strictly forbidden to make independent decisions regarding patient care. However, the development of nursing, the struggle for human rights in the world, including in our country, have become an incentive for change in one of the main medical professions. A nurse is becoming more independent in her work. Until recently, patient care was largely intuitive or empirical (when nurses relied more on practical, often routine experience or observations than on scientific research). Through trial and error, a nurse found means that were supposed to help a patient, and many nurses became professionals thanks to the accumulating experience of patient care.

Previously, nursing received a scientific basis either from the field of medicine (medical care), or from the field of physiology, biology, psychology, sociology. Now nursing strives to create its own unique knowledge base. Some aspects of patient care practice have not been fully developed and are solved at an intuitive level, but the basis of the scientific approach in this area has already been created and will be developed. It should be taken into account that "the pace of development of nursing depends on practice, so one can observe significant variations between its various areas, as well as its features in different countries ... At different times, nurses performed (and still perform) the work of doctors, dieticians, cleaners and clerks ... All this brings confusion to the understanding of the unique role of the nurse," wrote F. Nightingale. According to her, one can come to the conclusion that nursing means caring for a person, and not just solving his medical problems - "it is better to know a person in a certain state than the state itself that brings him suffering"

The time when a nurse's work was mainly limited to helping a patient wipe sweat from his face is passing. Today, she still carries out the doctor's orders, but is becoming more and more independent in making independent decisions.

Indeed, today nursing is both an art and a science. It requires both understanding and application of special knowledge and skills. Nursing is based on theory and practice, created on the basis of the humanities and natural sciences: biology, medicine, psychology, sociology, etc. The nurse accepts responsibility and acts with due authority in the direct performance of professional duties and is accountable for the health care services provided. She has the right to decide for herself whether she needs further education in management, teaching, clinical work and scientific research and to take steps to meet these needs. The mission of nursing in society is to help individuals, families and groups develop their physical, mental and social potential at an appropriate level, regardless of changing living and working conditions. This requires nurses to work to promote and maintain health and to prevent disease.

New Nursing is a need to change the basis of current practice. The organization of nursing activities is based on the implementation of doctor's orders, on care, which pays attention to the individual needs of the patient.

The new concept will replace the long-established hierarchical and bureaucratic system of organizing nursing with a professional model. A highly qualified practicing nurse should have sufficient knowledge and skills to plan, implement and evaluate the results of care that meets the needs of a particular patient. At the same time, special emphasis is placed on the unique contribution of nursing care to the recovery and restoration of the patient's health.

From the history of medicine, we know that patients needed and received help and treatment long before nursing officially became a specialty. Until the end of the 19th century in the West and until the 1930s in Russia, family members usually nursed sick relatives themselves, and hospitals were intended only for the poor or people with significant mental disabilities. And today, the family is still the most accessible "health service" in the world.

Recently, the concept of the functions of a nurse has changed. If earlier it was focused on patient care, now a nurse, together with other specialists, considers the main task to be maintaining health, preventing diseases, ensuring maximum independence of a person in accordance with his individual capabilities. However, in most countries, including Russia, inpatient care and treatment are still considered preferable.

What is the mission of a nurse? It is to help individuals, families, and groups of people define and achieve physical, mental, and social health in the changing conditions of the environment in which they live and work. "This will require nurses to perform certain functions that promote and maintain health, as well as prevent disease. Nursing includes the planning and implementation of care during illness and rehabilitation, affecting not only the physical, but also the psychological and social aspects of a person's life, which make up his or her whole. All these aspects to some extent affect a person's health, illness, disability, or death."

The functions of a nurse follow from the mission of nursing in society. They are of great importance regardless of the place (home, work, school, university, prison, refugee camp, hospital, clinic, and other places) and time of care, the severity of the patient's condition, or his or her financial situation. The nurse should actively involve the patient in self-care, and his family members and friends in caring for him. She should help him to maintain his independence and autonomy.

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